

Comparative Evaluation of Gate Driving Schemes for Paralleled 2.3 kV SiC MOSFET Power Modules

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Abstract—Parallel operation of SiC MOSFET power modules is required in high-power converter systems for increasing the power rating. However, current imbalance may cause power derating due to excessive device temperature, while differential-mode gate-source voltage oscillations can become severe and potentially lead to device failure. These issues highlight the critical role of the gate driving scheme in ensuring stable and reliable parallel operation. This article presents a quantitative comparison of three gate driving schemes using experiments performed on two paralleled SiC MOSFET modules. The results provide practical guidance for selecting appropriate gate driving schemes and making informed design trade-offs in high-power applications.

Index Terms—Silicon carbide (SiC) MOSFETs, power modules, parallel connection, current sharing, gate driver, differential-mode oscillation.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the increasing demand for higher-voltage and higher-power converter systems in applications such as wind energy, energy storage, and hydrogen electrolysis, the development of SiC multichip power modules has attracted significant attention from both academia and industry [1]–[6]. Leading device manufacturers have continuously released SiC power modules with higher voltage ratings and current capabilities [7]–[10]. Nevertheless, to achieve megawatt-level power transmission, further parallelization of multichip power modules is still required for converter designers [11]–[13].

Power converters with paralleled SiC modules face two main challenges, which are current imbalance during the switching transition and static operation, as well as divergent oscillations [14]. Both issues can de-rate the module operating capability, which needs to be taken care beforehand during the design phase.

Gate driving schemes have important impact on the final electrical performance of paralleled SiC MOSFET modules. In the literature, three typical gate driving schemes for paralleled modules can be identified [15]:

1) *Multiple-driver approach*: A multiple-driver approach, where each module has its own dedicated driver, eliminating common gate paths and enhancing stability, but requiring precise synchronization [16];

2) *Single-driver approach*: A single-driver approach, where one driver distributes gate signals symmetrically to all modules, offering simplicity and cost advantages but suffering from layout constraints and potential circulating currents [17]. This

Fig. 1. Conceptual diagram of paralleled SiC MOSFETs, illustrating the power loop connections by busbar and three typical gate driving schemes for gate loop connection.

method is commonly used in paralleled discrete devices since it offers compactness [13].

3) *Master-slave approach*: A master-slave approach, which combines scalability and modularity by distributing signals from a central master to local slave boards, while posing higher requirements on power supply and system integration [18].

Although experimental demonstrations of paralleled SiC power modules using each gate driving scheme have been reported in the literature, claiming satisfactory performance in current sharing, switching behavior, and EMI, these studies remain case-specific [7], [17], [19]. A systematic understanding of different gate driving schemes, along with unified evaluation metrics and a fair comparative study, is still missing. Therefore, this work differentiates three representative gate driving schemes for paralleled SiC modules, proposes a comprehensive evaluation matrix, and validates the analysis experimentally using two paralleled 2.3 kV Infineon modules. The results provide practical guidance for converter engineers in selecting suitable gate driving schemes during the design phase.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION

As illustrated in Fig. 1, the power terminals of paralleled MOSFETs are connected through busbars, and their gate and Kelvin source terminals are controlled by gate drivers. The gate driving scheme determines their gate loop connections between the devices. The gate loop between MOSFETs can be fully isolated, if multiple drivers are applied or fully connected if MOSFETs share one common driver. The gate loop impedance

Fig. 2. Typical turn-on switching transitions of paralleled SiC MOSFETs, illustrating major challenges: current imbalance and differential-mode oscillations.

directly affects the gate-source voltage and the device current, which ultimately determine the switching performance.

Fig. 2 shows the turn-on switching transitions of paralleled SiC MOSFETs to demonstrate the major challenges.

Current imbalance is a primary issue. During the current rising stage, the devices can have different current slew rates. This is caused by gate signal delays and device mismatches, such as threshold voltage (V_{th}) and transconductance (g_m), leading to dynamic current imbalance. During the steady-state stage, static current imbalance occurs due to variations in on-state resistance ($R_{DS(on)}$) and asymmetric busbar layouts.

Differential-mode gate voltage oscillation is another major challenge when paralleling SiC MOSFETs. These oscillations can become unstable and eventually cause device failure. The gate and Kelvin-source impedances directly influence this system stability [14], [20]. Therefore, a properly designed gate driving scheme is required for the reliable operation of paralleled SiC MOSFETs.

III. OVERVIEW OF GATE DRIVER STRUCTURE

In this section, the typical gate driver structure for a single SiC MOSFET is first analyzed, and a unified definition is established for subsequent discussion. Building on this basis, three gate driving schemes for $N \times$ paralleled SiC MOSFET power modules are introduced, with consistent terminology. The distinctions among these schemes are also clarified to facilitate a systematic comparison.

A. Gate Driver for Single MOSFET

A typical gate driver structure for SiC MOSFET power modules is introduced to illustrate the essential functions of the driver. As shown in Fig. 3, it consists of four key parts: a DC–DC isolated power supply, PWM signal interface, gate driver IC stage, and fault protection circuit [21].

1) *Master board*: In this article, the master board includes the power supply and PWM transmission. The isolated DC–DC power supply (PS) is an essential block in gate drivers, providing the appropriate voltage levels for SiC MOSFET operation and ensuring galvanic isolation. PWM control signals are commonly transmitted via optical fibers to achieve noise-immune modulation.

2) *Slave board*: The slave board consists of a driver stage and a protection circuit. The driver stage (DS) is responsible for sourcing and sinking the required gate charge to switch

Fig. 3. Typical gate driver structure for one SiC MOSFET.

Fig. 4. Conceptual diagram of three gate driving schemes for N paralleled MOSFETs: (a) N -Master/ N -Slave/ N -Module, (b) 1-Master/1-Slave/1-Extension/ N -Module, and (c) 1-Master/ N -Slave/ N -Module.

MOSFETs on and off, where a totem-pole buffer stage is typically employed. In the literature, this stage is often referred to as a “buffer.” The protection circuit detects abnormal conditions such as short circuits, overvoltage, and overcurrent, and generates feedback signals to protect the device. In advanced driver ICs, several protection functions are integrated; however, in this work, they are illustrated separately for clarity.

B. N -Master/ N -Slave/ N -Module Gate Driving Scheme

A straightforward gate driving scheme for paralleled SiC MOSFETs is assigning an independent gate driver to each

device, as illustrated in Fig. 4(a) [16]. In this scheme, SiC MOSFETs are connected in parallel only via their drain and source terminals through the DC-link and output busbars, while the gate and Kelvin-source nodes of each module remain entirely separate from any common connection. This isolation of the gate paths minimizes cross-coupling and interaction among the modules, at the expense of increased driver count and system complexity.

C. 1-Master/1-Slave/1-Extension/N-Module Gate Driving Scheme

In this scheme, all paralleled power modules share a common power supply, PWM input, and driver stage, as illustrated in Fig. 4(b). The gate signals are then distributed to each module locally through an extension board. Since the driver and protection are centralized, additional local protection circuits are usually required to ensure accurate fault detection at the module level. A practical implementation of this scheme for hard paralleling of SiC MOSFET modules has been demonstrated by Infineon [17], where the shared driver structure is applied in industrial power module applications.

D. 1-Master/N-Slave/N-Module Gate Driving Scheme

In contrast to the fully independent or fully shared gate driving schemes, another modular and scalable scheme has been illustrated in Fig. 4(c). In this scheme, all modules share a common isolated power supply and control signal interface provided by a so-called master board, while each module is equipped with its own local driver board. The local driver boards are connected in cascade, distributing symmetrical gate signals to each module and ensuring consistent propagation paths.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL VERIFICATION

In this section, two 2.3 kV SiC MOSFET modules are paralleled using three different gate driving schemes.

A. Gate Driver Design

Photos of the two modules equipped with the three gate driving schemes are shown in Fig. 5. The master, slave, and extension boards are highlighted using different colors for clarity. For all schemes, the turn-on and turn-off gate resistances are uniformly set to $3.3\ \Omega$ and $5\ \Omega$, respectively. Additionally, a $1\ \Omega$ Kelvin-source resistor is included [22].

B. Module Under Test

Infineon 2.3 kV SiC MOSFET half-bridge modules are used in this article [7]. They are housed in a $100\ \text{mm} \times 140\ \text{mm}$ XHP™2 package. These power modules feature a nominal current rating of 1500 A and a low $R_{DS(on)}$ ($1.27\text{--}1.59\ \text{m}\Omega$). They are specifically designed for emerging high-power applications, such as wind power generation and energy storage systems.

Two modules (labeled as Module 1 and Module 2) are selected for the experiments and characterized using a Keysight B1506A power device analyzer [23]. Their measured static characteristics are presented in Fig. 8 to Fig. 9. The results

Fig. 5. Photographs of different gate driving schemes for two paralleled SiC MOSFET power modules: (a) 2-Master/2-Slave/2-Module; (b) 1-Master/1-Slave/1-Extension/2-Module; (c) 1-Master/2-Slave/2-Module gate driving scheme.

indicate that their V_{th} and g_m are nearly identical. However, there is an approximate 2% difference in their $R_{DS(on)}$, with module 1 exhibiting a slightly higher resistance than module 2.

C. Double Pulse Test Platform

Double pulse tests (DPT) are conducted to evaluate the impact of different gate driving schemes on the switching performance. The experimental setup is shown in Fig. 6, and the measurement equipment details are summarized in Table I. Fig. 7 presents the physical layout of the DC-link capacitor busbars and the load inductor connections.

Fig. 6. Photo of double pulse test bench.

 TABLE I
 COMPONENTS FOR THE DOUBLE PULSE TEST SETUP

Equipment/Component	Key Parameters
Micsig Rogwski probes for i_{ds1} and i_{ds2} [24]	1200 A / 10–30 MHz
LeCroy HVD3605A for v_{ds1} and v_{ds2} [25]	6 kV / 100 MHz / ≤ 5 pF
Micsig MOIP350P for v_{gs1} and v_{gs2} [26]	350 MHz
LeCroy WaveRunner 8058HD [27]	500 MHz

Fig. 7. DC-link busbar layout demonstration, and the double pulse test setup connection illustration, with load inductor located in the center.

Since the $R_{DS(on)}$ is extremely low (m Ω level), contact resistance must be controlled. Therefore, all power terminal screws were tightened to an identical torque using a torque wrench during assembly. Additionally, the load inductor was connected at the midpoint between the two modules to ensure symmetrical current paths. One limitation of this setup involves the Rogowski coils used for high-current measurements. These sensors are susceptible to electromagnetic noise and measurement drift. To address this issue, zero-drift compensation was applied to the measured current waveforms during data processing.

D. Evaluation Metrics

The performance indicators used for comparing different gate-driver schemes are defined in this subsection. These indicators are selected to reflect the essential requirements of parallel operation in high-power SiC MOSFET modules, namely: safe and stable switching without derating and improved current sharing among devices.

1) *Differential Mode Stability*: Parallel operation of SiC MOSFET modules can give rise to differential-mode oscillations, which are mainly triggered by asymmetry [11], [28]. These oscillations appear as divergent gate-source voltage (v_{gs}) waveforms among modules, often showing near 180°

 Fig. 8. $R_{DS(on)}$ characteristics of two SiC MOSFET modules.

Fig. 9. Transfer characteristics of two SiC MOSFET modules.

Fig. 10. Transconductance characteristics of two SiC MOSFET modules.

phase position as shown in Fig. 11. If left uncontrolled, they may cause excessive voltage stress, or even device failure. In this work, the stability of the gate-source voltage is used as a performance indicator. Specifically, the damping ratio (ζ) is extracted from the transient v_{gs} waveforms, providing a

Complete double-pulse test waveforms highlighting dynamic and static intervals

Fig. 11. Detailed double pulse test waveforms, illustrating the definition of each evaluation metric.

quantitative measure of robustness of each scheme.

2) *Dynamic Current Sharing*: Dynamic current imbalance refers to the mismatch of MOSFET currents during switching transitions. This imbalance can arise from unsynchronised gate control signals and the distributed device parameters, such as threshold voltage (V_{th}) and transconductance (g_m), as expressed in Eq. (1). Several metrics can be used to quantify dynamic current sharing performance, such as di/dt or the peak current (I_{pk}). However, in this paper, the difference in switching losses is adopted as the evaluation criterion. The reason is that, while the current imbalance reflects the instantaneous non-uniformity, it is ultimately the uneven switching energy dissipation that leads to temperature divergence among devices. This temperature imbalance, in turn, introduces practical reliability concerns, as illustrated in Fig. 11.

$$i_d = g_m (v_{gs} - V_{th}) \quad (1)$$

3) *Static Current Sharing*: The static current sharing performance is evaluated by the average current deviation among parallel MOSFETs during the steady on-state period, when the devices are fully turned on with a constant gate-source voltage. In this stage, the primary sources of mismatch are the variations in the $R_{DS(on)}$ of MOSFETs and the differences in the power loop layout.

4) *Cost*: The bill of material (BOM) cost is a decisive factor when comparing different gate-driver solutions, since it directly determines the economic feasibility of large-scale adoption.

 Fig. 12. Experimental turn-on waveforms of two paralleled SiC MOSFETs under the *N*-Master/*N*-Slave/*N*-Module gate driving scheme, tested at a DC-link voltage of 1500 V and a total load current of 1500 A.

Therefore, BOM cost is included as a performance indicator in this paper to provide a fair assessment of both the technical and economic aspects of different schemes.

E. Results

The turn-on switching waveforms obtained from the experiments are shown in Fig. 12 to Fig. 14. Based on these results, the performance of each scheme is summarized in Table II, where the evaluation is conducted according to the defined performance metrics.

1) *2-Master/2-Slave/2-Module scheme*: In this scheme, the master and slave boards are completely independent. Consequently, the gate and source loops of the two paralleled MOSFETs are fully isolated with no direct electrical connection. Because of this isolation, only common-mode oscillations are observed on the gate-source voltage (v_{gs}), while differential-mode oscillations are entirely eliminated.

However, dynamic current imbalance is clearly observed during the switching transient, as shown in Fig. 12, which is attributed to a propagation delay difference in v_{gs} between the two modules. Measurements using passive probes indicate a delay mismatch of approximately 4 ns. It is assumed that this discrepancy is from the manufacturing tolerances of the optical fiber transceivers and the gate driver ICs. In future optimizations, this delay can be mitigated using active gate driving techniques or compensated through FPGA-based timing tuning [29], [30].

TABLE II
COMPARISON OF GATE DRIVING SCHEMES FOR TWO PARALLELED SiC MOSFET POWER MODULES

Gate driving scheme (N=2)	Differential-mode stability	Dynamic current sharing	Static current sharing	Cost ^a
N-Master / N-Slave / N-Module	Stable (1500 V/1500 A)	22.9% Loss deviation	4.4% difference (33 A)	High
1-Master / 1-Slave / 1-Extension / N-Module	Unstable (1500 V/1500 A)	7.28% Loss deviation	3.3% difference (25 A)	Low
1-Master / N-Slave / N-Module	Stable (1500 V/1500 A)	5.79% Loss deviation	2.8% difference (21 A)	Medium

^a Cost indicators: High / Medium / Low correspond to relative hardware cost.

Fig. 13. Experimental turn-on waveforms of two paralleled SiC MOSFETs under the 1-Master/1-Slave/1-Extension/N-Module gate driving scheme, tested at a DC-link voltage of 1500 V and a total load current of 1500 A.

2) *1-Master/1-Slave/1-Extension/2-Module scheme*: This scheme demonstrates good dynamic current sharing performance, because the current rising edges of the two modules nearly overlap, as shown in Fig. 13. However, 180° out-of-phase (differential-mode) oscillations are observed on v_{gs} , and their amplitude increases with the load current. Furthermore, this scheme necessitates symmetrical PCB routing for the gate-source loops. This layout complexity scales up dramatically as the number of paralleled devices increases. The another weakness of this scheme is one gate driver IC drive two modules at the same time, which shows slower switching speed compared to others, even with the same gate resistance.

3) *1-Master/2-Slave/2-Module scheme*: This scheme achieves both good current sharing performance and stable switching transitions, as illustrated in Fig. 14. In this scheme, the paralleled MOSFETs share the power supply and PWM control signals from a single master board, while each module is driven by its own local slave board. Consequently, the gate

Fig. 14. Experimental turn-on waveforms of two paralleled SiC MOSFETs under the 1-Master/N-Slave/N-Module gate driving scheme, tested at a DC-link voltage of 1500 V and a total load current of 1500 A.

loops of the two modules are effectively decoupled, which mitigates differential-mode oscillations. Simultaneously, the shared master signals ensure highly synchronized driving, preserving the excellent dynamic current sharing.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper experimentally compared three gate driving schemes for two paralleled 2.3 kV SiC MOSFET power modules. The results indicate that the 1-Master/N-Slave/N-Module scheme provides the optimal balance of performance and practicality. It achieves stable switching transitions and balanced current sharing, while maintaining cost-effectiveness and design simplicity, compared to the N-Master/N-Slave/N-Module and 1-Master/1-Slave/1-Extension/N-Module schemes. Although the experimental validation in this article focuses on a two-module setup, the recommended driving scheme is scalable and can be readily extended to applications requiring more than two paralleled devices.

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